

Title: Applications & use cases of blockchain in industrial settings"

Name:[Dan Giurescu](#)

Affiliation:Member at The A100, Blockchain Consultant & Advocate

BIOGRAPHY:

Dan Giurescu

Founder of Terrahub, industrial blockchain education and incubator in Calgary Alberta. Dan is a dynamic, insightful and collaborative business leader with demonstrated success identifying market opportunities where others may not, and capitalizing on them. With a depth of well-rounded energy industry experience, Dan leverages his financial acumen, regulatory knowledge, and technology expertise to further organizational efficiencies, mitigate risk, and maximize profits.

Dan thrives on the challenge of commercializing new concepts, guiding teams and inspiring action by creating an environment where taking risks in pursuit of success is encouraged. Dan is a Member of [The A100](#) and Mentor with [IBM District Ventures](#).